

DEFINITION OF TERMS IN THE LEGAL LEXICON

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Abstract. *The meaning of a term connects it with a professional, scientific or technical concept, the meaning of a non-term word connects it not only with an everyday concept or a general idea, but also with an emotion, a strong-willed impulse, an aesthetic experience.*

Key words: *correlation, boundary, stylistic, receptive, pragmatic, strategic, paradigmatic, consolidation, perceptual, object, phenomenon, polysemy, homonymy.*

The term that works in the context of everyday communication or in literary texts expresses a general idea, and the border between the everyday concept and the general idea is quite arbitrary, it consists of the level of materiality of the reflected features: the everyday concept is characterized by a high level of tolerance, approximation, closeness to the features of the object. In turn, the term differs from the everyday concept by the greater materiality of the reflected properties of the object, the degree of penetration into the essence of the reflected objects.

According to T.A. Zhuravleva, the semantic features of the word term can be reduced to the following in comparison with the meaning of the common word:

1) the meaning of the word term connects it, first of all, not with a separate object, but with their class, category, type; the meaning of a non-term word primarily associates it with a specific thing, object, property, process, etc., although in some contexts a non-term word is associated with a concept or general idea;

1) 1) the meaning of the word term connects it with a professional, scientific or technical concept, the meaning of a non-term word connects it not only with an everyday concept or a general idea, but also with an emotion, volitional impulse, aesthetic experience;

2) the meaning of the term connects it with the need to define it; the meaning of a word that is not a term has no such correlation, although the definition allows it;

3) the meaning of the word term can rise to higher levels of abstraction from reality and even break ties with it; the meaning of a non-term word, as a rule, remains at lower levels of abstraction from reality;

4) the meaning of the term is related to a certain professional activity; the meaning of a non-term word is related to the non-professional needs of human communication. (Juravleva, 1995:22-23)

The definition of term and term boundary aims to define the boundaries of the vocabulary to be included in the terminological dictionary. According to the words of V.M. Pererva, "based on the definition of the term we adopted, it seems appropriate to include the concepts of "lower limit" and "upper limit" of the term, which allows for practical solutions to some issues of selection (Pererva, 1976: 193). In the terminological dictionary, according to the definition of the term, only the words representing a certain scientific concept, that is, words - terms, are selected. Ordinary words of the language are not included in the terminological dictionary and remain outside the defined limits.

But it should be remembered that in some cases a simple word of the language acquires a terminological meaning (one or more), that is, a word with one or more meanings becomes a term. In this case, one of the most common methods of term formation is borrowing by revising common words

in the language (Budagov, 1965: 25-26). For example, the widely used word remedy - "disease treatment, drug, ointment" - began to be used as a legal term as a "judicial protection tool, legal protection tool", the commonly used word "chair" as a legal term "Amer. electric chair", "a place occupied by a person with a high position: a throne, a seat in parliament, a judge's seat, etc.", "a high position", "a court; position of judge"; "Amer. chair"; "authority; began to be used as the position of mayor.

The "upper limit" of the term V.M. According to Pererva, free combination of terms and terms, more precisely, the boundary between complex and compound terms as a lexical phenomenon included in the dictionary, and syntactic association of separate terms as a speech phenomenon, was left out of the dictionary. (Pererva, 1976:194)

In this study, we use the information provided in the Russian-English and English-Russian legal dictionaries, but it should be noted that the number of free combinations of terms is almost unlimited, and therefore it is very difficult to set an "upper limit" for the term. That is why we follow the classification proposed by O.D. Mitrofanova.

According to the words of O.D. Mitrofanova, its semantic and etymological features, the lexical composition of the scientific text goes back to three sources:

- real terms (highly specialized vocabulary);
- semantically specialized words of the common language (finished words);
- words of common language used in generally accepted meanings. (Mitrofanova, 1985: 156).

A dictionary of terminological character, many terms formed in the language of a certain science do not go beyond this language. It should be noted that due to the increase in the level of knowledge of native speakers and the strengthening of the scientific-technical interaction of colloquial speech, a large number of terms enter the common language and develop secondary lexical meanings without separating from "terminological" semantics. "We believe that the semantics of the word is divided into lexical concept and lexical background. Each word summarizes, that is, names a class of objects or phenomena, therefore, a concept is a sum of some semantic parts, with the help of which a person determines whether a certain object belongs to the set (class) considered by this name". (Kulebakin, 1968:69)

The semantics of the word belongs to the public mind, that is, it is common to all members of a certain national culture, respectively, to all native speakers of the national language. The semantics of the term belongs only to specialists, so it has a group character, not a national one. Thus, professional training is nothing more than mastering the semantics of terms (not only concepts, but also backgrounds to one degree or another). "Step-by-step introduction of the student to the group by mastering the semantics of the language of the group. This diagram shows the relationship between the lexical concept and background area (A), the scientific concept and background area (C) and their intersection area (B). Area of intersection (B) can be related to vocationally oriented lexis area, which area B is important for the teacher in teaching vocationally oriented lexis. It should also be noted that most of the scientific terms are the so-called finishing words of the common literary language. Both terms themselves and ending words play an important role in understanding professional literature, as well as in teaching communication on professional topics. These two groups are called occupationally oriented lexicon in this study.

When teaching the vocabulary of any language, difficulties arise in learning the volume of word meanings, which in many cases do not correspond to the native language, the multiple

meanings of words, the nature of harmony of some words with others, as well as the use of words in certain situations of communication. Polysemy and homonymy are characteristic of the English language. When semantically close words are represented by words of English and French origin, such phenomena are also manifested with difficulty. For example, theft, abbrochment.

Professionally oriented legal lexicon in English has its own characteristics compared to general literary vocabulary.

The nature of the professionally oriented legal lexicon of the English language is such that a stable phrase, an expression, often acts as a unit of meaning, so the use of the term "lexical unit" is legitimate. We consider a language unit that has an independent lexical meaning and is capable of performing the function of a speech unit as a lexical unit. (Azimov, Shchukin, 1999: 133) lexical components of professionally oriented lexicon and terminology are the most specific part of professionally oriented lexicon and include more or less set phrases. For example, *неглигенсэ — небрежность; negligence - небрежность; negligence per se - отсутствие обычной меры заботливости; gross negligence грубая небрежность; active negligence - небрежность, выразившаяся в действии; passive negligence - небрежность, выразившаяся в бездействии.*

The most important element of the lexicon of jurisprudence is a term as a set of meanings denoting a concept specific to the field of law. Legal lexical terminology is one of the most important components of the terminology of social sciences, and its formation and development is related to the complex interrelationship of extralinguistic and linguistic factors. A distinctive feature of the development and evolution of professional English legal lexicon, especially in the field of international law and human rights, is great dynamism, a large number of word combinations and a high intensity of language exchange.

When talking about a professional-oriented dictionary, it is impossible not to mention such a concept as the lexical-semantic field. The lexical-semantic field is a complex organic whole capable of self-development. The Cambridge Encyclopaedia defines the semantic or lexical domain as "the domain of meaning in which lexemes interact and define each other in a particular way" (Crystal, 1995: 157).

In Russian linguistics, the term "field" is usually understood as "a set of linguistic (mainly lexical) units united by a common content (sometimes by common formal indicators) and reflecting the conceptual, subject or functional similarity of defined phenomena." (Yartseva, 1998:380)

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